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TASHQI MUHIT BILAN O‘ZARO TA’SIR QILUVCHI STERJENLAR YUKLANISHIDA ELASTIK VA ELASTIK PLASTIK TO‘LQINLAR

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Annotatsiya. Amalda grunt ichidagi sterjen va sterjenlar sistemasini hisoblash bilan bog‘liq turli xil muammolar yuzaga keladi. Quvur bo‘ylab plastik deformatsiyalarning rivojlanishini tahlil qiluvchi masalalar kam o‘rganilgan. Bundan tashqari, sterjen deformatsiyasining tabiatiga sterjenni o‘rab turgan gruntning xususiyatlari sezilarli darajada ta’sir ko‘rsatadi. Ushbu holat vaqt bo‘yicha o‘zgaruvchan yuklar, xususan seysmik kuchlar ta’siri ostida to‘lqin jarayonlarining shakllanishi va tarqalishi dinamikasini batafsil tahlil qilishni talab qiladi. Ushbu maqolada sterjen tashqi muhit bilan Vinkler qonuniga muvofiq ta’sirlashuvchi, materiali ikki modulli chiziqli qonunga bo‘ysinuvchi, uchiga qiymati keskin o‘zgaruvchi lahzali va vaqtga bog‘liq yuklar ta’sirida yarim cheksiz uzunlikdagi elastik-plastik doiraviy sterjenlardagi bir o‘lchovli to‘lqin tarqalish jarayonlari, yani plastik deformatsiyalar tarqalish masalasi ko‘rib chiqilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: sterjenlar tizimi, grunt, plastik deformatsiya, to‘lqin hosil bo‘lish va tarqalish dinamikasi.

Masalani qo‘yilishi. Tashqi muhit bilan Vinkler qonuni asosida o‘zaro ta’sirda bo‘lgan, sterjenning materiali Prandtl qonun bo‘yicha deformatsiyalanadigan, yarim cheksiz sterjenda to‘lqin tarqalish (telegraf) tenglamasini qaraymiz:

$$\rho F \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} - EF \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + \pi Dku = 0$$

$\tau = \frac{a_0 t}{L}$, $\xi = \frac{x}{L}$ o‘zgaruvchilarda sterjen zarrachalarining harakat differensial tenglamasi elastik-plastik va elastik sohalarida quyidagi ko‘rinishda bo‘ladi:

$$\frac{\partial^2 u_1}{\partial \tau^2} - \frac{\partial^2 u_1}{\partial \xi^2} + \lambda^2 u_1 = 0, \quad 0 \leq \xi \leq \gamma_0 \tau \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 u_2}{\partial \tau^2} - \gamma_0^2 \frac{\partial^2 u_2}{\partial \xi^2} + \lambda^2 u_2 = 0, \quad \gamma_0 \tau \leq \xi \leq \tau \quad (2)$$

bu yerda (τ, ξ) vaqt va koordinata, $\gamma_0 = \sqrt{\frac{E_1}{E}} < 1$, E, E_1 - sterjen materiali uchun elastiklik, plastiklik modullari, $\lambda^2 = \frac{\pi DkL^2}{EF}$, k - Vinkler koeffitsiyenti bo‘lib tashqi muhit ta’siridagi bir birlik kesim yuza (1m^2) va uzunligi (1 m) ga mos keladigan kuch, o‘lchov birligi $\frac{N}{\text{m}^3}$, gruntlar xossasiga bog‘liq $(5 \div 15) \cdot 10^6$ oraliqdagi qiymatlarni qabul qiladi, (L, D, F) - sterjen uzunligi, diametri va ko‘ndalang kesim yuzi, $u_1(\xi, \tau)$ va $u_2(\xi, \tau)$ mos ravishda elastik plastik va elastik sohalarida sterjen kesimlarining ko‘chishlari. Koordinata boshini sterjenning chap uchiga joylashtirib, 0 ξ o‘qini sterjen o‘qi bo‘ylab o‘ng tomonga yo‘naltiramiz. Chegaraviy va ko‘chishlarning uzluksizlik shartlari quyidagicha bo‘ladi:

$$\xi = 0 \text{ bo‘lganda } \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial \xi} = f(\tau) \quad (3)$$

$$\xi = \gamma_0 \tau \text{ bo'lganda } u_1 = u_2, \quad (4)$$

bundan tasqari elastik to‘lqin frontida $\xi = \gamma_0 \tau$ quyidagi shart bajarilishi lozim:

$$\frac{\partial u_1}{\partial \tau} = -(1 - \gamma_0) \varepsilon_s - \gamma_0 \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial \xi} \quad (5)$$

(1) va (2) differensial tenglamalarni yechimini quyidagi ko‘rinishda izlaymiz [1]:

$$u_1 = - \int_0^{\gamma_0 \tau - \xi} \psi'(z) J_0(\lambda \sqrt{(z - \gamma_0 \tau)^2 - \xi^2}) dz - \int_0^{\gamma_0 \tau + \xi} \chi'(z) J_0(\lambda \sqrt{(z - \gamma_0 \tau)^2 - \xi^2}) dz, \quad (0 \leq \xi \leq \gamma_0 \tau) \quad (6)$$

$$u_2 = - \int_0^{\tau - \xi} \varphi'(z) J_0(\lambda \sqrt{(z - \tau)^2 - \xi^2}) dz, \quad (\gamma_0 \tau \leq \xi \leq \tau) \quad (7)$$

(6) va (7) ni (3)-(5) shartlarga qo‘yib, $\varphi'(z)$ va $\psi'(z)$ funksiyalar $\xi = \gamma_0 \tau + 0$, $\xi = \tau + 0$ xarakteristikalar bo‘ylab nolga, ya‘ni $\psi'(-0) = 0$, $\varphi'(-0) = 0$ ekanligidan (3)- (5) shartlarni quyidagicha yozamiz:

$$\psi'(\gamma_0 \tau) - \chi'(\gamma_0 \tau) = f(\tau) \quad (8)$$

$$\int_0^{2\gamma_0 \tau} \chi'(z) J_0(\lambda \sqrt{(z - \gamma_0 \tau)^2 - \gamma_0^2 \tau^2}) dz = \int_0^{(1-\gamma_0)\tau} \varphi'(z) J_0(\lambda \sqrt{(z - \tau)^2 - \gamma_0^2 \tau^2}) dz \quad (9)$$

$$\chi'(2\gamma_0 \tau) + \frac{\lambda}{2} \int_0^{2\gamma_0 \tau} z \chi'(z) \frac{J_1(\lambda \sqrt{(z - \gamma_0 \tau)^2 - \gamma_0^2 \tau^2})}{\sqrt{(z - \gamma_0 \tau)^2 - \gamma_0^2 \tau^2}} dz = \chi_0 \quad (10)$$

$$\chi_0 = \frac{1 - \gamma_0}{2\gamma_0} \varepsilon_s \quad (11)$$

(10) integral tenglamada $J_1(z)$ Bessel funksiyasini ikkita hadi bilan chegaralanib, $\lambda < 1$ va $s = 2\gamma_0 \tau$ almashtirishlar olsak quyidagi integral tenglamani hosil qilamiz:

$$\chi'(s) + \frac{\lambda^2}{32} \int_0^s z \chi'(z) [8 - \lambda^2(z^2 - sz)] dz = \chi_0 \quad (12)$$

Hosil qilingan (12) integral tenglamadan s bo‘yicha 2 marta hosila olib, $\lambda < 1$ ekanligidan, λ^4 ga bog‘iq hadlarni tashlab $\chi(0) = 0$, $\chi'(0) = \chi_0$, $\chi''(0) = 0$ boshlang‘ich shartli differensial tenglamaga ega bo‘lamiz:

$$\chi'''(s) + \frac{\lambda^2 s}{4} \chi''(s) + \frac{\lambda^4 s^2}{32} \chi'(s) = 0 \quad (13)$$

Bu (13) tenglamani $\chi'(s) = \chi_0 \exp(-\frac{\lambda^2}{8} s^2)$ yechimida $\exp(-\frac{\lambda^2}{8} s^2)$ funksiyani qatorga yoyib λ^4 va undan yuqori darajali hadlarni tashlab yuborib quyidagini hosil qilamiz:

$$\chi(s) = \chi_0 \int_0^s \exp(-\frac{\lambda^2}{8} u^2) du \approx \chi_0 (s - \frac{\lambda^2}{24} s^3) \quad (14)$$

Aniqlangan $\chi(s)$ funksiya $\chi'(\gamma_0 \tau)$ hosilasini (8) ga qo‘yib $\psi(\gamma_0 \tau)$ funksiyani aniqlaymiz

$$\psi(z) = \chi_0 \left(z - \frac{\lambda^2}{24} z^3 \right) + \int f\left(\frac{z}{\gamma_0}\right) dz \quad (15)$$

Aniqlangan $\chi(z)$ funksiyasining (14) ifodasini va $J_0(z)$ Bessel funksiyasini ikkita hadi bilan chegaralanib (9) ga qo‘yamiz, $s_1 = (1 - \gamma_0)\tau$ almashtirish olib hosil bo‘lgan tenglamadan s_1 bo‘yicha 3-tartibli hosilasini olib $\lambda^4 \ll 1$ ekanligidan o‘zgaruvchi koeffitsiyentli, 3-tartibli chiziqli bir jinsli differensial tenglamaga ega bo‘lamiz, unda $\eta(s_1) = \varphi'(s_1)$ almashtirish olib 2-tartibli chiziqli bir jinsli differensial tenglamani hosil qilamiz, $y(x) = \eta(s_1)$, $x = s_1 \lambda \beta = s_1 \lambda \sqrt{\frac{\gamma_0}{2(1-\gamma_0)}}$ yangi o‘zgaruvchi kiritamiz, $a = \frac{1+2\gamma_0}{\gamma_0}$ belgilash quyidagi differensial tenglamaga ega bo‘lamiz:

$$y'' - xy' - ay = 0 \quad (16)$$

(16) differensial tenglamani yechim [8] adabiyotning 422-bet, 2.44 tenglamasida keltirilgan yechimga asosan quyidagicha yozamiz:

$$y(x) = C_1 \left(1 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{a(a+2)(a+4)\dots(a+2k-2)}{(2k)!} x^{2k} \right) + C_2 \left(x + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(a+1)(a+3)(a+5)\dots(a+2k-1)}{(2k+1)!} x^{2k+1} \right) \quad (17)$$

$y(0) = \varepsilon_s, y'(0) = 0$ chegaraviy shartlardan foydalanib, $C_1 = \varepsilon_s, C_2 = 0$ o‘zgarishlarni aniqlab (17) yechimni quyidagicha yozamiz:

$$\varphi'(s_1) = \eta(s_1) = \varepsilon_s \left[1 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\prod_{j=1}^k (a+2j-2)}{(2k)!} (\beta \lambda s_1)^{2k} \right] \quad (18)$$

bunda $a = \frac{1+2\gamma_0}{\gamma_0}, \beta = \sqrt{\frac{\gamma_0}{2(1-\gamma_0)}}$.

U holda (1) va (2) tenglamalar yechimi quyidagicha yozamiz:

$$u(\xi, \tau) = \begin{cases} u_1, & 0 \leq \xi \leq \gamma_0 \tau \\ u_2, & \gamma_0 \tau \leq \xi < \tau \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

bunda u_1, u_2 yechim (6) va (7) formulalar bilan, $\psi'(z), \chi'(z), \varphi'(z)$ funksiyalar (14), (15) va (18) formulalar bilan aniqlanadi, ya’ni (26) yechimni quyidagicha yozamiz:

$$u_1 = - \int_0^{\gamma_0 \tau - \xi} \left[\chi_0 \left(1 - \frac{\lambda^2}{8} z^2 \right) + f \left(\frac{z}{\gamma_0} \right) \right] J_0 \left(\lambda \sqrt{(z - \gamma_0 \tau)^2 - \xi^2} \right) dz - \chi_0 \int_0^{\gamma_0 \tau + \xi} \left(1 - \frac{\lambda^2}{8} z^2 \right) J_0 \left(\frac{\lambda}{\gamma_0} \sqrt{(z - \gamma_0 \tau)^2 - \xi^2} \right) dz, \quad 0 \leq \xi \leq \gamma_0 \tau$$

$$u_2 = - \int_0^{\tau - \xi} \varepsilon_s \left[1 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\prod_{j=1}^k (a + 2j - 2)}{(2k)!} (\beta \lambda s_1)^{2k} \right] J_0 \left(\lambda \sqrt{(z - \tau)^2 - \xi^2} \right) dz, \quad \gamma_0 \tau \leq \xi < \tau$$

$L = 5 \text{ m}, t = 0,001 \text{ s}; \tau_0 = 1; \gamma_0 = 0,6; \lambda = (0; 0,2; 0,4; 0,6; 0,8);$
 $a_0 = 5000 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}; \varepsilon_s = -0,0012$ qiymatlar asosida λ parametrlarning turli qiymatlarida deformatsiyalarning koordinata ξ bo‘yicha o‘zgarish grafiklari $f(\tau) = -e_0, f(\tau) = -e_0 + e_1 \tau$ bo‘lganda quyidagi rasmlarda keltirilgan.

$$f(\tau) = -e_0$$

$$e_0 = 0,002$$

$$f(\tau) = -e_0 + e_1\tau;$$

$$e_0 = 0,002; e_1 = 0,0005$$

Xulosa. Rasmda keltirilgan egri chiziqlar tahlilidan kelib chiqadiki, sterjen yuzasi va tashqi muhit o‘rtasidagi ta’sir mavjud bo‘lganda, uzunlik bo‘ylab kuchlanish taqsimotining to‘lqinli tabiati saqlanib qoladi. Elastik-plastik sohada $0 \leq \xi \leq \gamma_0\tau$ yuklash nuqtasidan dastlab qisman tushirish, keyin $e > e_0$ yuklash kuzatiladi. Elastik sohada $\gamma_0\tau \leq \xi < \tau$, aksincha, sterjen dastlab qisman yuklanadi va keyin siqish deformatsiyasiga e_0 tushiriladi. Plastiklik $0 \leq \xi \leq \gamma_0\tau$ sohasida deformatsiyani qiymatlarini pasayishini, elastiklik $\gamma_0\tau \leq \xi < \tau$ sohada esa deformatsiyani qiymatlari o‘zgarmasligini ko‘rish mumkin.

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